

MANAGEMENT OF OVARIAN CYSTS IN NEWBORNS

Sh.D. Babazhanova^{1,2}, F.A. Ibragimova^{1,2}, B.B. Ergashev^{1,2}

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan¹

Republican Perinatal Center, Tashkent, Uzbekistan²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15039904>

Abstract. *Due to more frequent ultrasound examinations of pregnant women and newborns, the frequency of detection of ovarian cysts in the fetus and newborn has increased. The aim of the study was to optimize the treatment and monitoring of newborns with ovarian cysts. The study included 68 pregnant women and their newborn girls with diagnosed ovarian cysts. Depending on the properties of ovarian cysts (“simple” or “complex” cysts, liquid or solid, suspicion of malignancy or no suspicion), the presence or absence of symptoms, and also taking into account the size of the formation, treatment can be surgical or conservative-observational. Surgical treatment of newborns was performed in 31 (45.5%) cases, in 9 cases - laparoscopically, in 22 cases - laparotomy with a paraumbilical circular incision or an inferomedial incision. In 83.8% of cases, organ-preserving operations were performed. Conservative tactics and observation were carried out in 37 cases (54.4%); in the dynamics of observation of these children, spontaneous regression was observed in 35 cases within 3-12 months. During surgical treatment, whenever possible, an organ-preserving method should be used, since preservation of ovarian tissue is important for preserving fertility and further full sexual development of the girl. The lack of a uniform approach to the treatment of ovarian cysts in newborns requires further research.*

Keywords: *newborns, ovarian cysts, cystadenoma, ovarian cyst torsion, diagnostics of ovarian cysts, surgical and conservative treatment of neonatal ovarian cysts.*

Introduction. Ovarian cysts are the most common abdominal masses in newborn girls, occurring at a rate of 1:2625 pregnancies, according to various authors [1,7,9]. Previously considered rare, the frequency of diagnosed ovarian cysts in fetuses and newborns has increased due to more frequent ultrasound examinations of pregnant women and newborns [1,9]. The first description of a neonatal ovarian cyst dates back to 1889 during a post-mortem examination of a premature baby born at 7 months who had died [6]. The etiology of ovarian cysts in fetuses and newborns is unknown, but there are suggestions that excessive stimulation by maternal and placental hormones leads to an increase in ovarian follicles, potentially causing tumor-like processes in the fetal ovaries [1,7,9]. Other factors may include maternal infections, genetic predisposition, and maternal hormone therapy [7,9]. Despite their frequency, there are no standardized methods for the diagnosis, treatment, and monitoring of ovarian cysts in fetuses and newborns. While some authors recommend conservative management for neonatal ovarian cysts [3,8], others advocate for more active surgical treatment [4,10], and there are even studies on intrauterine surgical treatment of fetal ovarian cysts [5].

Objective: To determine the current aspects of treatment and monitoring of newborns with ovarian cysts.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted at the Republican Perinatal Center from 2016 to 2024. It included 68 pregnant women and their newborn girls diagnosed with ovarian cysts. Pregnant women with diagnosed fetal ovarian cysts underwent ultrasound examinations

twice a month until delivery, while newborns were examined 48-72 hours after birth. Newborns managed conservatively were monitored monthly for the first six months and then every two months until the cysts resolved. Ovarian masses were classified as "small" if the ultrasound size was up to 40 mm, and "large" if the size was over 40 mm. Ultrasound evaluated the mass wall, presence of septa, solid components, cystic content characteristics (anechoic, ground-glass, hemorrhagic, mixed, inclusions), and vascularization using Doppler. Additionally, masses were classified based on ultrasound features as "simple" or "complex," unilocular, multilocular, solid, or mixed.

Results: Ovarian cysts were detected in fetuses after 28 weeks in all 68 cases. The average gestational age at detection was 31.4 ± 3.2 weeks (ranging from 28 to 37 weeks). Of the pregnant women, 29.4% were primiparous, 25.3% were in their second pregnancies, 35.4% in their third, and 9.9% in their fourth. The average diameter of the cysts ranged from 33 mm to 140.8 mm. In 86.7% of cases, the cysts were simple; the remaining 13.4% were complex with multiple compartments. During pregnancy, 47.1% of the cysts did not change in size, 39.7% increased in size, and 13.2% decreased. In 7.3% of cases, simple cysts became complex multilocular cysts. All cases were confirmed postnatally by ultrasound. In 54.1% of cases, deliveries were via cesarean section due to obstetric indications; the rest were vaginal deliveries. 79.4% of the newborns were full-term, while 21.6% were premature. The average weight of full-term infants was 3778.5 ± 226.7 g, and the average weight of premature infants was 2438 ± 203.7 g. In 70.5% of cases, the cyst was in the right ovary, and in 29.5% in the left ovary. Surgical treatment was performed in 45.5% of cases: 9 via laparoscopy and 22 via laparotomy with a paraumbilical circular incision or lower midline incision. In 3 cases of complex multilocular cysts, torsion was observed, and the cyst content was hemorrhagic, leading to salpingo-oophorectomy. Oophorectomy was performed in 2 cases of multilocular cysts. In the remaining 26 cases, cystectomy or ovarian resection was performed.

Clinical Case 1: A multiparous woman at 34 weeks' gestation was found to have an abdominal mass in the fetus measuring 55x34 mm. Diagnosis: Simple ovarian cyst. The cyst increased in size over time. The pregnancy was complicated by moderate anemia, gestational hypertension, acute polyhydramnios, and the woman received antihypertensive medications. At 27 and 35 weeks, she was treated for ARVI in the hospital. At 38 weeks, a cesarean section was performed (December 7, 2023). The female newborn, E.Z., birth history No. 5173, had a birth weight of 3879g and a length of 52 cm. Apgar score: 7/8 points. The baby's condition was severe due to respiratory failure grade 2, and she was transferred to the neonatal intensive care unit. St localis: the abdomen was oval, enlarged, and symmetrically shaped. Intestinal peristalsis was sluggish. The abdomen was soft and non-tender on palpation. Ultrasound: an abdominal mass measuring 101x52 mm with a thin-walled capsule was visualized. MSCT: a large round mass measuring 90x127x110 mm with clear, smooth contours and homogeneous content was seen in the anterior abdomen. The baby had Hb-145g/l, WBC-15.67. Clinical diagnosis: Giant abdominal cyst, ovarian cyst? Intestinal obstruction. The baby was prepared for surgery, and two days later, underwent "Lower midline laparotomy. Removal of right ovarian cyst with right ovarian resection." Intraoperatively, a right ovarian cyst measuring 125x90x100 mm was found, punctured, and 850 ml of clear serous fluid was drained. Histological diagnosis: serous ovarian cyst. The baby was discharged on the 9th postoperative day in satisfactory condition under pediatric and pediatric gynecologist supervision.

Fig.1. Ovarian cyst in child E.Z.

Fig.2. Ovarian cyst in child P.M.

Clinical Case 2: Second pregnancy, at 32 weeks an ovarian mass measuring 67x43 mm was detected. Over time, the cyst size slightly increased. The pregnancy was complicated by anemia, and the first trimester included moderate vomiting which was treated in the hospital. The baby was delivered at 40 weeks through natural birth on June 18, 2024. The baby's weight was 3992 g, height 53 cm, and the Apgar score was 8-9 points. St localis: On examination, the girl's abdomen was normal in shape and symmetrically involved in respiration. Bowel peristalsis was active, the abdomen was palpated as distended but non-tender, and a mass was palpable in the right iliac region. Ultrasound data: a cystic mass measuring 93.9x54.6 mm, anechoic, unilocular, with thin walls was detected in the abdomen. Simple ovarian cyst on the right. Due to the absence of symptoms and the mother's refusal of surgical treatment, the child was discharged home on September 24, 2024. Two days later, the mother and child returned to the perinatal center due to the child's discomfort. The child's condition was satisfactory. An operation "Laparoscopy. Right ovarian cystectomy" was performed. The child was discharged home in satisfactory condition on the 5th day under the supervision of a pediatrician and pediatric gynecologist.

Clinical Case 3: B.Sh., medical history No. 538. At 32 weeks, an ultrasound detected a fetal abdominal cyst measuring 54x37 mm with thin walls and anechoic, unilocular content. Diagnosis: Simple ovarian cyst. Over time, the cyst size increased. The pregnancy proceeded normally, and delivery occurred at 40 weeks through natural birth on June 18, 2024. The baby weighed 3890 g and was 55 cm tall, with an Apgar score of 8/9 points. Ultrasound data: a cystic mass measuring 63.4x44.6 mm, anechoic, with thin walls, was detected in the abdomen. Simple ovarian cyst on the right. Due to the absence of symptoms, it was decided to monitor the cyst conservatively. Over 3 months, the cyst size increased. The mother and child were admitted to the perinatal center on September 23, 2024. Upon admission, the child responded to the examination with restlessness. St. Localis: On examination, the abdomen was enlarged and distended, symmetrically involved in respiration; the child responded to palpation with painful crying, bowel peristalsis was active, stool regular, urination free and independent, and a mass measuring approximately 120x70 mm was palpable in the abdomen. Ultrasound data: a cystic mass with smooth, clear contours measuring 127x82.7 mm and 1.7 mm thick walls, with anechoic content, was visualized in the right side of the abdomen. MSCT data: an oval-shaped cystic mass measuring 108x66x100 mm with smooth thin walls was detected at the entrance to the pelvis. Diagnosis: Right ovarian cyst. CBC: Hb-95 g/L, WBC-9.82. Diagnosis: Giant right ovarian cyst. Moderate anemia. On September 26, 2024, an operation "Paraumbilical laparotomy. Right ovarian cystectomy. Abdominal sanitation and drainage" was performed. The cyst content was serous, with 920 ml of fluid. The child was discharged home on the 4th day in satisfactory condition under the supervision of a pediatrician and pediatric gynecologist.

Fig. 3. Ovarian cyst in child B.Sh.

Fig. 4. Ovarian cyst in child P.G.

Conservative management and observation were carried out in 37 cases (54.4%).

During the observation of these children, spontaneous regression was observed in 35 cases within 3-12 months, while in 2 cases, the ovarian cyst remained but was asymptomatic and did not increase in size.

Clinical Case 4: At 31 weeks of pregnancy, an abdominal mass in the fetus measuring 36x41 mm was detected. Diagnosis: Left ovarian cyst. Over time, the size of the mass did not increase. Delivery occurred on September 13, 2023, at 41 weeks of pregnancy. Medical history No. 3723, child P.G. The child's weight was 3720 g, height 53 cm, and Apgar score was 8/9 points. On examination: The abdomen was slightly enlarged, soft, non-tender, with regular bowel movements and painless urination. A mass was palpable on the left side, non-tender. Ultrasound data: Left ovarian cyst measuring 41.8x70.6 mm. Blood tests were normal. The child was discharged home on the 5th day under observation. Monthly ultrasound was recommended for 6 months, and then every 2 months until the cyst disappeared or symptoms appeared. After 6 months, the ovarian cyst was no longer detected on ultrasound.

Discussion: Before routine ultrasound screening of pregnant women and newborns, ovarian cysts in newborns were usually detected when the mass was large and palpable during abdominal examination. With the implementation of screening schedules for pregnant women during pregnancy and newborn ultrasound screening, ovarian cysts are now detected more frequently [1,7,9]. However, detecting an ovarian cyst raises questions about managing the pregnancy and the postnatal care of the newborn girl with the cyst. Management issues arise because, in many cases, the child with an ovarian mass has no symptoms, yet many researchers emphasize that ovarian cysts have a high risk of complications such as torsion, ovarian necrosis, cyst rupture, infection, bowel obstruction, urinary problems, and potentially the need for ovary removal due to these complications [1,2,8,10]. As a result, many surgical operations are performed on asymptomatic ovarian cysts. For instance, Brandt ML et al. [2] reported on 257 cases of simple and complex ovarian cysts in children published between 1975-1990, including information on 170 infants who underwent ovarian surgery, with oophorectomy performed in 85.3% of cases (145 patients). Brandt ML et al. recommend surgical treatment for all complex cysts and simple cysts larger than 4 cm to prevent future ovarian torsion. Meanwhile, other authors report successful conservative management of neonatal and childhood ovarian cysts [3,7]. Currently, there are no unified guidelines for the treatment and management of neonatal ovarian cysts, and no standardized indications for surgical treatment based on the size or characteristics of ovarian masses. Some authors propose surgical treatment for all complex multilocular ovarian cysts. In our study, conservative management was successful in 54.5% of cases; we conservatively managed all "simple" asymptomatic cysts up to 8 cm and "complex" cysts up to 8 cm. The majority

of patients (35 out of 37 - 94.5%) managed conservatively showed regression of the ovarian cysts within one year. Additionally, there were no cases of malignancy in our study of newborns.

Conclusions: With the implementation of ultrasound screening for pregnant women and newborns, the frequency of detecting ovarian cysts in fetuses and newborns has increased. Depending on the characteristics of the ovarian mass (simple or complex cyst, fluid-filled or solid, suspected malignancy or not), the presence or absence of symptoms, and the size of the mass, treatment can be surgical or conservative-observational. When surgical treatment is necessary, an organ-preserving approach should be used whenever possible, as preserving ovarian tissue is important for maintaining fertility and normal sexual development in girls. The lack of a unified approach worldwide to the treatment of neonatal ovarian cysts requires further research.

REFERENCES

1. Akın MA, Akın L, Özbek S, Tireli G, Kavuncuoğlu S, Sander S, Akçakuş M, Güneş T, Öztürk MA, Kurtoğlu S. Fetal-neonatal ovarian cysts-their monitoring and management: retrospective evaluation of 20 cases and review of the literature. *J Clin Res Pediatr Endocrinol.* 2010;2(1):28-33. doi: 10.4274/jcrpe.v2i1.28. Epub 2010 Feb 4. PMID: 21274333; PMCID: PMC3005663.
2. Brandt ML, Luks FI, Filiatrault D, Garel L, Desjardins JG, Youssef S. Surgical indications in antenatally diagnosed ovarian cysts. *J Pediatr Surg.* 1991 Mar;26(3):276-81; discussion 281-2. doi: 10.1016/0022-3468(91)90502-k. PMID: 1827651.
3. Cesca E, Midrio P, Boscolo-Berto R, Snijders D, Salvador L, D'Antona D, Zanon GF, Gamba P. Conservative treatment for complex neonatal ovarian cysts: a long-term follow-up analysis. *J Pediatr Surg.* 2013 Mar;48(3):510-5. doi: 10.1016/j.jpedsurg.2012.07.067. PMID: 23480904.
4. Ciro E, Vincenzo C, Mariapina C, Fulvia DC, Vincenzo B, Giorgia E, Roberto C, Lepore B, Castagnetti M, Califano G, Escolino M. Review of a 25-Year Experience in the Management of Ovarian Masses in Neonates, Children and Adolescents: From Laparoscopy to Robotics and Indocyanine Green Fluorescence Technology. *Children (Basel).* 2022 Aug 12;9(8):1219. doi: 10.3390/children9081219. PMID: 36010109; PMCID: PMC9406417.
5. Diguisto C, Winer N, Benoist G, Laurichesse-Delmas H, Potin J, Binet A, Lardy H, Morel B, Perrotin F. In-utero aspiration vs expectant management of anechoic fetal ovarian cysts: open randomized controlled trial. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol.* 2018 Aug;52(2):159-164. doi: 10.1002/uog.18973. Epub 2018 Jul 4. PMID: 29205608.
6. Dornan A.N. Large ovarian tumors in 7 month old child. *Trans. Path. Soc., London,* 1889.
7. Erol O, Erol MB, Isenlik BS, Ozkiraz S, Karaca M. Prenatal diagnosis of fetal ovarian cyst: case report and review of the literature. *J Turk Ger Gynecol Assoc* 2013;14(02):119–122
8. Rajeswaran PK, Sivanandam S, Arunachalam P. A Case Series of Fetal-Neonatal Ovarian Cyst from a Tertiary Care Hospital. *J Lab Physicians.* 2023 Jun 13;15(4):596-601. doi: 10.1055/s-0043-1768947. PMID: 37780874; PMCID: PMC10539059.
9. Rotar IC, Tudorache S, Staicu A, Popa-Stanila R, Constantin R, Surcel M, Zaharie GC, Mureşan D. Fetal Ovarian Cysts: Prenatal Diagnosis Using Ultrasound and MRI, Management and Postnatal Outcome-Our Centers Experience. *Diagnostics (Basel).* 2021 Dec 31;12(1):89. doi: 10.3390/diagnostics12010089. PMID: 35054256; PMCID: PMC8775004.

10. Xue-Qiang Y, Nan-Nan Z, Lei Y, Wei L, Hong-Qiang B, Jun Y, Xu-Fei D, Xin-Ke Q. Management of ovarian cysts in infants. *J Res Med Sci.* 2015 Dec;20(12):1186-90. doi: 10.4103/1735-1995.172988. PMID: 26958055; PMCID: PMC4766827.